

**DEVELOPMENT DIRECTIONS AND CURRENT ISSUES OF GREEN
ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN**

**YASHIL TADBIRKORLIKNING O‘ZBEKISTONDAGI RIVOJLANISH
YO‘NALISHLARI VA DOLZARB MASALALARI**

**НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ И АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЗЕЛЕНОГО
ПРЕДПРИНИМАТЕЛЬСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ**

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Annotatsiya

Ushbu havola etilayotgan maqolada O‘zbekistonda yashil tadbirkorlikning zamonaviy holati, rivojlanish tendensiyalari va istiqbollari tadqiq etilgan. Shuningdek, yashil iqtisodiyot tamoyillarini joriy etish jarayonidagi asosiy muammolar va to‘siqlar, hamda ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari tahlil qilingan.

Qolaversa, O‘zbekiston uchun yashil tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish strategiyasi taklif etilgan bo‘lib, u mamlakatimizning iqlim o‘zgarishlari va ekologik muammolarga qarshi kurashish hamda barqaror rivojlanish yo‘lidagi xalqaro majburiyatlariga asoslangan. Qarorlar qabul qilish jarayonida yashil texnologiyalarni joriy etishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini baholash metodologiyasi ham keltirilgan. Tadqiqotimiz so‘ngida O‘zbekistonda yashil biznesning kelgusi o‘n yillikdagi istiqbollari baholanib, yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirish bo‘yicha tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar:

Yashil tadbirkorlik, barqaror rivojlanish, qayta tiklanuvchi energiya, resurs samaradorligi, ekologik innovatsiyalar, raqobatbardoshlik, yashil investitsiyalar

Аннотация

В данной статье исследуется современное состояние, тенденции развития и перспективы «зелёного» предпринимательства в Узбекистане. Также

проанализированы основные проблемы и препятствия в процессе внедрения принципов зелёной экономики, а также пути их преодоления. Кроме того, предложена стратегия развития зелёного предпринимательства для Узбекистана, основанная на международных обязательствах страны в области борьбы с изменением климата и экологическими проблемами, а также устойчивого развития.

В процессе принятия решений приведена методология оценки экономической эффективности внедрения зелёных технологий. В заключение исследования оценены перспективы зелёного бизнеса в Узбекистане на ближайшее десятилетие и разработаны рекомендации по развитию зелёной экономики.

Ключевые слова:

Зелёное предпринимательство, устойчивое развитие, возобновляемая энергия, ресурсная эффективность, экологические инновации, конкурентоспособность, зелёные инвестиции

Abstract

This article examines the current state, development trends and prospects of green entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan. The main problems and obstacles in the process of implementing green economy principles, as well as ways to overcome them, are analyzed. The article proposes a strategy for the development of green entrepreneurship for Uzbekistan, based on the country's international commitments to combat climate change and environmental problems, as well as sustainable development.

The methodology for assessing the economic efficiency of implementing green technologies in the decision-making process is also presented. At the end of the article, the prospects for green business in Uzbekistan for the next decade are assessed, and recommendations for the development of the green economy are developed.

Keywords:

Green entrepreneurship, sustainable development, renewable energy, resource efficiency, environmental innovations, competitiveness, green investments

Introduction

As we all know, one of the most important global challenges of the 21st century is ensuring economic development in the context of climate change and environmental crisis. The international community widely recognizes the necessity of transitioning to a "green" development path, where economic growth is achieved without harming the environment and depleting natural resources. In particular, "green entrepreneurship is a business activity that stimulates economic growth without causing environmental damage and serves sustainable development."¹

As we know, Uzbekistan has been implementing large-scale reforms in recent years aimed at modernizing the economy and integrating into the international community. At the same time, our country faces a number of serious environmental challenges, such as the consequences of the Aral Sea desiccation, water resource scarcity, soil degradation, air pollution, and the impact of climate change on agriculture. In this regard, our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev emphasizes: "We must widely introduce the principles of green economy into practice and further expand the use of renewable energy sources. In this regard, we must act proactively without any hesitation."² This situation demands new approaches based on sustainable economic development and active implementation of "green" technologies.

It would be no exaggeration to say that the adoption of the Republic of Uzbekistan's Strategy for Transition to a "Green" Economy for 2019-2030 provided a strong impetus for the development of green entrepreneurship in the country. Within the framework of this program, significant projects are being implemented in numerous areas, including

¹ <https://www.oecd.org/greengrowth/towardsgreengrowth.htm>

² From the speech delivered by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, at the 75th session of the United Nations General Assembly, September 2020.

enhancing energy efficiency, expanding the use of renewable energy sources, effective water resource management, waste recycling, and many other directions. However, there are still challenges that need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of green entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan.

The role of transitioning to a "green" economy and the active implementation of green technologies in solving such problems is invaluable. Our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev also describes this as follows: "The path to sustainable development is the path of 'green' development."³

Specifically, green entrepreneurship is developing in the following main areas:

- 1) **Energy efficiency and renewable energy** – new technologies based on solar, wind, hydro, and bioenergy, implementation of energy-saving systems
- 2) **Resource efficiency and waste-free production** – resource recycling, waste management, and use of secondary raw materials
- 3) **Organic agriculture** – cultivation of environmentally clean food products
- 4) **Green construction** – construction based on energy and resource efficiency

Organic Agriculture

There are great opportunities for the development of organic farming in Uzbekistan. Since 2022, the Law "On Organic Agriculture" has been in effect in the country, which establishes the procedures for producing, certifying, and marketing organic products. Currently, projects for growing organic fruits, vegetables, and medicinal plants are also being implemented in the Fergana Valley, Samarkand, and Jizzakh regions.

³ <https://president.uz/uz/lists/view/6805>

Literature Review

During our research, we utilized numerous outstanding works by renowned scholars as well as the decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on the development of green economy.

Below, you can familiarize yourself in detail with these sources and their significance.

In our article, we used Muhammad Yunus's work "A World of Three Zeros." This work encompasses three main directions of contemporary economics – eliminating poverty, eradicating unemployment, and achieving zero carbon emissions. Furthermore, during the writing of our article, we also reviewed the Republic of Uzbekistan's Strategy for Transition to a Green Economy 2019-2030.

This strategic document establishes a clear roadmap for implementing green technologies, protecting the environment, and achieving sustainable development goals in our country. Additionally, the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 (Decree No. PF-60) also defines modern directions of state policy. This document serves to demonstrate practical mechanisms for integrating green economy principles into the national development program and determines the relevance of the research topic.

Analysis and Results

In our research, we selected SWOT analysis as one of the most effective methods for assessing the state and prospects of green entrepreneurship. This is because it helps identify strengths and weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.

SWOT Analysis

Table 1

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Large potential of renewable energy resources (solar, wind) – Due to its geographical location, Uzbekistan has the opportunity to generate significant amounts of solar and wind energy annually. ➤ Availability of government support programs – Government strategies and financial incentives aimed at developing the green economy are driving this sector forward. ➤ Large-scale economic reforms – Modernization processes undertaken in recent years are creating a favorable environment for green business. ➤ Large young population and potential consumers – A significant portion of the population consists of young people who show interest in new technologies and ecological 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Shortage of qualified personnel in the green business sector – There are few specialists with specific knowledge and experience in green entrepreneurship. ➤ Low environmental awareness among the population – Most citizens do not sufficiently understand the importance of green products and environmentally clean production. ➤ Inadequate infrastructure – The necessary infrastructure for implementing ecological technologies in practice has not yet been fully developed.

products.	
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Expanding international cooperation and attracting foreign investment – There is an opportunity to work with foreign investors and donors in the green business direction. ➤ Creating new jobs in the field of green technologies – This sector generates new professions and innovative forms of employment. ➤ Increasing export potential (organic products, renewable energy) – Green products are in high demand in the international market, expanding export opportunities. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Intensifying competition in the international market – The green products market is highly competitive, making it difficult to occupy strong positions for export. ➤ Intensification of climate change and environmental problems – Water scarcity, drought, and natural disasters may hinder the implementation of green projects. ➤ Intensifying competition in the international market – The green products market is highly competitive, making it difficult to occupy strong positions for export. ➤ Dependence on imports of green technologies – Due to weak domestic production, there is high dependence on importing technologies from abroad. ➤ Impact of economic crises –

	Global or regional financial crises may lead to a reduction in green investments.
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The conducted SWOT analysis demonstrates that Uzbekistan has significant opportunities for developing green entrepreneurship. However, at the same time, there are a number of problems and obstacles. Therefore, conducting an in-depth analysis of strengths and weaknesses while minimizing risks is of crucial importance in developing green entrepreneurship.

Discussion

As you can see, as a result of our scientific research and analysis of the development process of green entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan, a number of important innovations and opportunities have been identified. The adoption of the state's strategy for transitioning to a green economy, the increase in numerous investments, and the development of environmental awareness among our youth are creating a solid foundation for green entrepreneurship.

Renowned world scholars and economists have expressed the following views on the crucial importance of green entrepreneurship and sustainable development:

Research by Nobel Prize laureate and social entrepreneurship theorist Muhammad Yunus demonstrates that "The business world should be directed not only toward profit

but also toward solving social problems. Green entrepreneurship means taking responsibility for future generations."⁴

Harvard Business School Professor Michael Porter, who often speaks about competitive advantages and creating shared value, emphasizes that "The most successful companies are those that integrate social and environmental needs into their business strategy."⁵

Columbia University Professor Jeffrey Sachs states in his scholarly work that "The greatest opportunity for 21st-century entrepreneurs lies in developing green technologies and sustainable business models."⁶

The views presented above establish important guiding principles for the development of green entrepreneurship in the Uzbekistan context. Furthermore, they clearly demonstrate how crucial it is to develop green entrepreneurship not only in Uzbekistan but throughout the entire world.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, Uzbekistan possesses the necessary potential for developing green entrepreneurship. To fully realize this potential, the following measures may be effective:

— Strengthening government support mechanisms; — Attracting financial and investment resources; — Training qualified personnel; — Implementing innovative technologies; — Raising public environmental awareness.

⁴ Muhammad Yunus "Creating a World Without Poverty: Social Business and the Future of Capitalism" (2007)

⁵ Michael Porter Harvard Business Review "Creating Shared Value" (2011) 89(1/2), 62-77.

⁶ Jeffrey Sachs "The Age of Sustainable Development" (2015)

After all, as Klaus Schwab, founder of the World Economic Forum, emphasizes: "Competitive economies of the future will be green, innovative, and socially responsible economies."⁷

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⁷ Klaus Schwab (2016). "The Fourth Industrial Revolution"

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